

Exploring the Hidden Role of Filamentous Fungi in Sinusitis and Tonsillitis: A Study Using Molecular Diagnostic Techniques

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the presence of filamentous fungi pathogens in patients clinically suspected of having fungal sinusitis and fungal tonsillitis. One hundred fifty-five clinical specimens were collected from Al-Muanai Educational Hospital and Al-Basrah Teaching Hospital, they underwent clinical evaluations and laboratory tests to confirm the diagnosis. Direct microscope examination was conducted for each sample using KOH (10%) and lactophenol cotton blue and culturing on SDA, PDA. The current study showed 25 (16.12%) of the specimens positive for culture. Where all positive specimens were *Aspergillus* genus 24 (96%) and only one was *Rhizopus oryzae* 1 (4%), Which were diagnosed genetically.

Keywords: *Filamentous Fungi, fungal sinusitis, fungal tonsillitis, Aspergillus allahabadii, Aspergillus tubingensis, Aspergillus sydowii.*

Introduction

Fungal sinusitis, affecting primarily immunocompromised individuals, presents as inflammation of the sinus mucosa due to various fungi such as *Aspergillus*, leading to symptoms like chronic headaches, facial swelling, and thick purulent nasal discharge (Waghray, 2018). There are several different types of sinusitis; Acute, chronic, subacute and recurrent (Sachdev, 2023).

Chronic invasive fungal sinusitis (CIFS) is a serious condition that is increasingly prevalent, particularly among immunosuppressed patients, and often presents with prolonged symptoms that can be non-specific, complicating diagnosis (Ning, et al., 2021). Chronically invasive diseases, though less common, are characterized by persistent tissue invasion and can be classified into granulomatous and non-granulomatous types based on histopathological features (Bahethi, et al., 2023).

Noninvasive fungal sinusitis consists of three main subtypes: saprophytic fungal infections, fungus balls, and allergic fungal rhinosinusitis (AFRS) (Goyal, et al., 2023). *Aspergillus* species and *Mucorales* are indeed the leading culprits in cases of acute invasive fungal sinusitis (AIFS), particularly in immunocompromised patients. However, the use of azole prophylaxis can lead to the emergence of atypical fungal pathogens (Fung, et al., 2019). *A. flavus* is indeed a significant pathogen associated with invasive pulmonary aspergillosis (IPA), particularly in immunocompromised individuals. However, it is less frequently implicated in bronchopulmonary infections compared to *A. fumigatus*, which is the more common species responsible for such infections due to its higher prevalence in the environment and more aggressive

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pathogenic profile (Stemler, et al., 2023). *A. niger* caused infected in lung and paranasal sinuses (Stemler, et al., 2023).

Recurrent tonsillitis involves repeated episodes of inflammation and infection of the palatine tonsils (Klagisa, et al., 2022). Chronic and recurrent tonsillitis can substantially impact a child's quality of life by causing persistent sore throats, difficulty swallowing, and general discomfort, which can lead to missed school days, reduced participation in play and social activities (Abu Bakar, et al., 2018). Aspergillosis of the palatine tonsils is a rare fungal infection predominantly seen in immunocompromised individuals, such as those with HIV, cancer, or undergoing immunosuppressive treatment, due to their decreased ability to mount an effective immune response against *Aspergillus* species (Swain, & Debta, 2020).

The study aims to determine the cases of fungal sinusitis and tonsillitis.

Material and Methods

One hundred fifty- five clinical specimens were collected from Al-Muanai Educational Hospital and Al-Basrah Teaching Hospital from 5. September to 1. November. 55 (35.48%) sinusitis swabs, 60 (38.71%) tonsillitis swabs with 35 (22.58%) biopsies for tonsils and 5 (3.23%) biopsies for sinuses removed from patients by surgery). The patients ages were ranged from 4 to 42 years.

Filamentous Fungi Isolation

The swabs samples were transferred to the Mycology Laboratory in the Biology Department, the University of Basrah. Direct microscopic examination was carried out (Khalid, et al., 2021). The swabs from the sinusitis and tonsillitis were culture on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) with Chloramphenicol and on Sabouraud 's Dextrose agar (SDA) with Chloramphenicol, incubated for (1-14) days at 37°C (Chakrabarti, & Shivaprakash, 2008), after incubated can noted growth. Subculturing was carried out to isolate pure colonies, which were then preserved in slant culture at 4°C for subsequent analysis.

Filamentous Fungi Identification

1. Classical methods by Morphological identification

Filamentous fungi are effectively identified by examining their morphological features, under compound examination, with reference to established mycological identification guides to ensure accuracy (Guarro, et al., 2012; Jayasiri, et al., 2019).

2. Molecular identification

The DNA was extracted using the Gsync™ DNA extraction kit from Geneaid, followed by PCR amplification of the conserved ITS regions with universal primers (ITS1F-5' -TCC GTA GGT GAA CCT GCG G -3') 19Base, and (ITS4F- 5' - TCC TCC GCT TAT TGA TAT GC -3') 20Base. The PCR products were visualized with a Smart Blue™ transilluminator and their fragment sizes measured against a 100 bp DNA ladder. These amplified products were then sent for Sanger sequencing to Macrogen in Korea to obtain the nucleotide sequences.

Result

Direct Examination

The detection of 5% fungal hyphae and conidia under 10x and 40x magnification suggests the presence of a fungal infection or contamination.

Fungal Identification Methods

1. Classical methods by Morphological identification.

The sinusitis swab results show a predominance of negative findings (83.6%), with a small proportion testing positive for fungi, primarily *Aspergillus* species (*A. fumigatus*, *A. niger*, *A. terreus*, and *Aspergillus* spp.), accounting for 16.36%. Specifically, *Aspergillus* spp. were identified in 9 cases, representing 16.36%, with *A. terreus* and *A. fumigatus* being the most common. In contrast, sinus biopsy results indicate a higher rate of negativity (80%) with only 20% testing positive, notably for *Rhizopus* spp. Figure 1.

The phenotypic examination results for tonsillitis specimens reveal that swab samples had an 80% negative rate and a 20% positive rate, with *Aspergillus* species identified in a small proportion of positives, predominantly *A. fumigatus*. Conversely, tonsil biopsy specimens showed a higher negative rate (91.4%) and a lower positive rate (8.6%), with similar *Aspergillus* species detected (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Statistical Analysis Indicates No Significant Association between Filamentous Fungi Identification by Morphological Methods and the Different Clinical Samples, as Evidenced by p-values of 0.117 for Sinusitis Swabs, 0.287 for Sinus Biopsies, 0.417 for Tonsillitis Swabs, and 0.757 for Tonsil Biopsies

***Rhizopus oryzae*:** A filamentous fungus with dense, branching colonies that range from white to grayish, displays hyphae resembling tangled threads, giving it a distinctive texture. Its reproductive structures, sporangia, are typically black or dark brown and contain spores produced internally, facilitating its propagation (Figure 2).

Figure 2. (A) Showed *R. Oryzae*, Growing on SDA after Incubation 5 Days Using a 9 mm Petri Dish and (B), in Microscope Examination with Lactophenol Cotton Blue Showed (⇒) Aplanospore. (40x)

New record isolates

During the phenotypic examination, colony forms of filamentous fungi were observed, which were later identified genetically. Depending on specific morphological and molecular characteristics.

1- *Aspergillus allahabadii*: Is characterized by rapid colony growth with a cottony texture, featuring a pink center and white edges, and tending toward dryness. Its conidiophores display a range of colors, and the conidia are small, rounded, and densely packed, contributing to the colony's overall dense and distinctive appearance (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The Images Depict (A) *A. Allahabadii* Growing on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) after 5 Days Using a 9 mm Petri Dish and (B) after 10 Days of Incubation, Showing Progressive Fungal Growth with Characteristic Colony Morphology, such as a Velvety or Granular Surface, Possibly with Pigmentation. (C) The Microscopic Examination with Lactophenol Cotton Blue Stain at 40x Magnification Reveals (⇒) the Conidia, (⇒) Conidiophores and (⇒) Phialides

2-*Aspergillus tubingensis*: Displays a distinctive colony morphology marked by rapid growth, dense branching, and a color spectrum from dark brown to black, reflecting its vigorous nature. Its conidiophores are notably brown, supporting its identification, while the conidia are generally globose or sub-globose, contributing to its characteristic appearance. Figure (4)

Figure 4. (A) Showed *A. tubingensis* Growing on SDA after Incubation 5 Days Using a 9 mm Petri Dish, (B) Microscopic Examination of the Fungus Using Lactophenol Cotton Blue Stain at 40x Magnification Reveals (→) the Conidia and (→) Conidiophores

3- *Aspergillus sydowii*: Typically displays a woolly colony morphology with colors ranging from white to grayish and greenish-blue, marked by rapid growth and reproductive structures such as green-hued conidiophores with white margins. Its conidial heads are generally globose or sub-globose, with small conidia, making these features characteristic and useful for identification in laboratory cultures. as depicted in figure (5).

Figure 5. (A) *A. sydowii* Cultured on SDA after Incubation 5 Days Using a 9 mm Petri Dish and (B), Microscope Examination with Lactophenol Cotton Blue Stain at 40x Magnification Reveals (→) the Conidia , (→) Conidiophores and (→) Phialides

Molecular Identification

DNA Extraction (Gsync™ DNA extraction kit), Geneaid.

The 25 filamentous fungi isolates were subjected to molecular diagnostic techniques to confirm their accurate identification, as depicted in figure (6).

Figure 6. Agarose Gel Electrophoresis with a (0.8 %) Gel Concentration is Suitable for Analyzing Genomic DNA Extracted from Filamentous Isolates

Polymerase Chain Reaction

The PCR amplification results using primers ITS1-ITS4 demonstrated successful detection of fungal DNA in the isolates, with filamentous fungi producing bands approximately 600-700 bp, as shown in figure (7). This indicates that the primers effectively amplified the ITS regions, facilitating accurate identification of fungal species based on their amplicon sizes.

Figure 7. Agarose Gel Electrophoresis (2%) of PCR Product of Filamentous ITS Regions: Lane M:3000bp DNA ladder

Analysis for Sequencing of genomic space

After sending all the 25 isolates to Macrogen company in Korea for Sanger sequencing. <https://www.macrogen.com/en/main>, obtained and receiving the results, it became clear that the most common genera were *Aspergillus* include 7 species and *R. oryzae*.

Genetic Identification of Filamentous Fungi Typically Involves DNA-Based Methods

The data indicates that in sinusitis patients, the prevalence of *Aspergillus* species (*A. tubingensis*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. niger*, *A. sydowii*, and *A. terreus*) ranged from 1.8% to 5.5%. Additionally, *R. oryzae* was isolated from a 16-year-old patient, representing 20% of biopsies, as in table (1).

The genetic analysis of isolates from tonsils swabs revealed a diverse presence of *Aspergillus* species with *A. fumigatus* being the most common at 8.4%, followed by *A. terreus* at 6.7%, and others like *A. allahabadii*, *A. flavus*, and *A. niger* each around 1.7%, Conversely, tonsil biopsy samples showed a more uniform distribution among three species, *A. terreus*, *A. fumigatus*, and *A. niger*, each at approximately 2.9%, as in table (1)., where table (2) shows the genetic sequence of the four filamentous fungi mentioned.

Table 1. The Distribution of Genetically Filamentous Fungi Significantly Depended on the Location of Specimen Collection

Infected site	<i>A. allahabadii</i>	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>A. tubingensis</i>	<i>A. sydowii</i>	<i>A. terreus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>R. oryzae</i>	P. value
Sinusitis swab	0%	3.60%	1.80%	1.80%	5.50%	3.60%	0%	0%	0.071
Sinus biopsy	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	20%	0.302
Tonsillitis swab	1.70%	8.40%	0%	0%	6.70%	1.70%	1.70	0%	0.921
Tonsil biopsy	0%	2.90%	0%	0%	2.90%	2.90%	0%	0%	1.000

Table 2, offers comprehensive details on 25 filamentous fungi isolates, including their diagnostic classifications and NCBI accession numbers, which are essential for researchers to verify genetic information and pursue further studies in mycology, taxonomy, and related fields.

Table 2. BLAST Results our Isolates with Reference copy from NCBI Database

	Sample ID	Percentage of Identity %	Accession Number in NCBI	Scientific Name	Reference Copies (NCBI)
1	R1	No.		<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	KP329617.1
2	R4	100%	PV361447	<i>Aspergillus sydowii</i>	HQ637368.1
3	R5	100%		<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	OP651030.1
4	R6	100%		<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	MW193125.1
5	R7	100%		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	MH911384.1
6	R8	100%		<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	MG569674.1
7	R9	100%		<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	MK793187.1
8	R10	100%		<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	OP651030.1
9	R11	100%		<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	MW193125.1
10	R12	100%		<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	MW193125.1
11	R13	100%		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	MH911384.1
12	R14	100%		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	MT796796.1
13	R15	100%		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	MT796796.1
14	R16	100%		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	ON530861.1
15	R17	100%		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	MH880190.1
16	R20	100%		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	ON530861.1
17	R21	99.60%	PV361453	<i>Aspergillus allahabadii</i>	MK424488.1
18	R23	100%		<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	MT796796.1

19	R24	100%		<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	PQ394972.1
20	R25	100%		<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	OQ980627.1
21	R26	100%	PV368357	<i>Aspergillus tubingensis</i>	MT322427.1
22	R27	100%		<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	KP172477.1
23	R28	100%		<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	JF436885.1
24	R29	100%		<i>Aspergillus terreus</i>	JX427026.1
25	R30	100%	PV361454	<i>Rhizopus oryzae</i>	JN226941.1

Discussion

Fungal pathogens, despite their infrequent involvement in sinus and tonsillar infections, are gaining increased recognition because conventional antifungal treatments often prove ineffective, highlighting potential misdiagnoses or overlooked fungal causes (Yang, et al., 2021; Abbas, 2020).

The studies Yang, et al., (2021) and Abbas, (2020) highlight significant discrepancies between clinical diagnosis and laboratory culture results, with Yang's study showing approximately 27.7% (127/459) and Abbas's around 48% (60/125) of samples testing negative by culture, suggesting potential limitations of culture methods or the presence of alternative diagnostic challenges in accurately identifying the pathogens in these clinical specimens.

The study's successful identification of filamentous fungi strains at the species level via BLAST analysis against the GenBank database demonstrates the effectiveness of molecular methods in fungal taxonomy, aligning with study (Shokohi, et al., 2010), who also highlighted the critical role of DNA sequencing in accurately diagnosing fungal pathogens.

The study succeeded identified filamentous fungi using BLAST analysis, revealing *A. fumigatus* (63.3%) as the most common species. This highlights the importance of molecular methods in diagnosing fungal infection, especially in septic arthritis (Koutserimpas, et al., 2021).

A. terreus follows at (10%), with *A. niger* and other species present in equal proportions, underscoring the importance of targeting *A. fumigatus* in diagnostic and treatment strategies, particularly given the rising number of immunocompromised patients susceptible to such infections. Additionally, *R. oryzae* was identified in (4%) of the filamentous fungi isolates, emphasizing the diversity of pathogenic fungi in the studied context. This study underscores notable differences in the identification of filamentous fungi from sinusitis cases compared to study (Al-Saad, 2015), which relied solely on phenotypic methods, revealing *A. flavus* as the most prevalent at (28.5%), followed by *R. oryzae*, with an isolation and diagnosis rate of (20%), closely aligning with study Al-Saad, (2015) findings, although the current approach may offer more accurate or comprehensive identification.

A. allababadii, a rare species has historically been associated with environmental niches and recent findings suggest it may act as an opportunistic pathogen, especially in immunocompromised patients. Isolation of *A. allababadii* from tonsillitis swabs raises the possibility that it could contribute to invasive fungal tonsillitis, highlighting the need for further research to understand its pathogenic potential and implications for diagnosis and treatment in susceptible patient populations, *A. allababadii* are enigmatic and rare species, with limited data available due to their elusive habitat in underwater sediments off Jaeju-do Island in Korea (Hwang, et al., 2019).

The identification of *A. tubingensis* from sinus infection specimens, corroborates previous research by study Gautier, et al., (2016), which identified this species as a pathogenic agent contributing to sinusitis. Where it was shown, the clinical data indicate that *A. tubingensis* is frequently associated with chronic respiratory infections, affecting (75%) of the studied patients, with half experiencing acute exacerbations, suggesting its potential role in worsening respiratory symptoms. Additionally, its identification as a

causative agent in maxillary bone infections post-tooth extraction underscores its invasive capacity in craniofacial tissues (Kredics, et al., 2009).

A. sydowii as a widespread environmental fungus, often found in soil samples from the Basra Governorate (Kadhim, 2019) and plant sources like *Rhizopus epapposum* (Bushara, 2015). In this study is the first time it has been isolated from a pathological infection, sinus infection,

The overlap between clinical and environmental fungal isolates underscores the importance of further research into environmental reservoirs, as it suggests that fungi capable of existing harmlessly in nature can switch into opportunistic pathogens (Araújo, Souza, & Frases, 2017).

R. oryzae, a saprophytic and opportunistic fungus, is the main pathogen responsible for mucormycosis, notably the severe rhino- cerebral form that can be life-threatening, particularly when recovered from surgically removed sinus tissues, as this indicates invasive infection. Recent research by study Faiyazuddin, et al. (2023) highlights that *Rhizopus*-associated sinus infections predominantly affect immunocompromised individuals, including those with uncontrolled diabetes, patients undergoing immunosuppressive treatments such as corticosteroids and post-COVID-19 patients. Study results, the statement underscores the importance of prompt histopathological and mycological diagnosis in invasive fungal sinusitis, aligning with the 2018 ECMM guidelines, which emphasize that direct isolation from sinus tissue plays a critical role in confirming the diagnosis and facilitating timely treatment to reduce mortality (Cornely, et al., 2019). *R. oryzae*, demonstrates significant pathogenic potential due to its rapid growth at elevated temperatures, production of tissue-invasive enzymes like alkaline, catalase and protease and increased virulence in high free iron environments (Alqarihi, Kontoyiannis, & Ibrahim, 2023). These factors collectively enable the fungal to penetrate host tissues and evade immune defenses.

Conclusion

This study revealed the filamentous fungi as a causative agent of sinusitis and tonsillitis who underwent sinus and tonsil removed by surgery and have acute and chronic infections. After direct examination by the compound microscope and laboratory culture, it was found that the majority were *Aspergillus* spp, such as *A. allahabadii*, *A. fumigatus*, *A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *A. terreus*, *A. tubingensis* and *A. sydowii*. And can isolated *R. oryzae* from sinus biopsy, The isolates were phenotypically characterized and identified on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar and Potatoes Dextrose Agar. The diagnosis of these species was further confirmed through molecular identification.

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